

Proposal for the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Questionnaire

Supplementary material for the paper:

Converging towards a Semantic Interoperability Framework for EOSC: understanding the different community solutions

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Introduction

This document provides supplementary material for the paper ‘Converging towards a Semantic interoperability framework for EOSC: understanding the different community solutions to semantic interoperability’ submitted as a contribution to the 2nd Workshop on Ontologies for FAIR and FAIR Ontologies (Onto4FAIR)¹. Its purpose is to provide additional information and insights about the questionnaire approach proposed to survey the resources utilised by communities in addressing semantic interoperability issues. Originally conceived

¹ <https://onto4fair.github.io/2023-fois.html>

as a guidance document for implementing the questionnaire, this version reflects the current implementation and explains the rationale for it.

Questionnaire design

In the same manner as for recording the resources used for implementing the FAIR Principles in the FIP (FAIR Information Profile) approach (Magagna et. al., 2022), the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW)² is used as an interactive interface to guide the interviewee through the questionnaire. The advantage of this service is twofold. It provides a human-readable interface, which means that users can understand its aims and functionalities intuitively and interact with it. It also allows for a machine-readable output for a better comparability of the results. The result of the survey documents the resources used or planned to be used by a community to support semantic interoperability. For convenience, these resources will be referred to as FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs). The assumption is that resources supporting FAIR also encompass resources facilitating semantic interoperability. The aggregation of resources utilised by a community is referred to as a Semantic Interoperability Profile (SIP) of that community.

The FIP Ontology³ is extended with concepts and relations needed to address semantic interoperability aspects to provide a knowledge model configuring the DSW for the SIP. A FAIR Implementation Community is a collective of researchers collaborating in projects, initiatives or research infrastructure, aiming to set up a common strategy to implement a community specific Semantic Interoperability Framework. The community might have different interoperability case studies producing specific data types (e.g., text, images, data streams) for which it can provide specific Semantic Interoperability Profiles. For each specific question a community specifies the utilisation of FSRs through SIP declarations (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual model for the Semantic Interoperability Declaration

² <https://ds-wizard.org/>

³ <https://w3id.org/fair/fip/>

FSRs are described using nanopublications to provide a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier and machine-readable representation based on a FSR specific metadata schema. A nanopublication is a small unit of publishable information, with associated provenance, expressed as a RDF knowledge graph that is formal and machine-interpretable⁴.

The metadata schema for describing a FSR reuse existing ontological properties and is implemented as a nanopublication template. The FSRs for the SIP include semantic artefacts, crosswalks and metadata schemas but also the services used to create, transform, map, publish, register, and search them. Accordingly, the basic metadata schema includes the following fields (with * for mandatory metadata):

- Name of the resource (rdfs:label)*
- Short description (rdfs:comment)*
- FSR Types this resource represents* (rdfs:type)
- URL where the resource can be accessed (schema:url)
- URL of specification it is based on (e.g. schema) (doap:implements)
- URL to a website describing the resource (rdfs:seeAlso)
- Additional fields are used for each specific type.

Nanopublication descriptions for FAIR Supporting Resources can be created within the SIP Wizard environment and once created they are visible as drop-down options in the related questions. Having examples in the drop-downs for each question guides the user in answering it, making the interview more efficient.

The questionnaire has two main chapters:

- *General information* about the FAIR Supporting Community creating this SIP, the data type and case study that it represents, the time period for the validity of this SIP, the data registry used, the used data model and an overall community-wide approved practice for achieving semantic interoperability, if available.
- *Details on Semantic Interoperability*: the metadata schema, crosswalks, semantic artefacts and provenance model used, as well as supporting services for these artefacts.

⁴ <https://nanopub.net/>

Overview of FAIR Supporting Resource Types listed in the SIP:

main FSR	data	metadata	crosswalk	provenance	semantic artefact
FAIR Practice for Semantic Interoperability					
associated FSR	registry (repository)	metadata schema	metadata crosswalk	provenance model	controlled (structured) vocabulary
	data model	registry (repository)	data crosswalk	provenance tracking model	ontology
	FAIR representation service	knowledge representation language	editor		editor
		registry			
		Web-API			
		FAIR practice			
		validation service			

For each of the above listed FAIR Supporting Resource Types a common pattern of questions is used:

- Does your community use <FSR Type>?
 - No
 - Please describe community requirements and constraints leading to this answer (Considerations)
 - Yes
 - List the FSRs:
 - Select the FSR
 - The implementation choice is
 - Currently in use by the community
 - Currently in use but is planned to be replaced in the future
 - Select the replacement FSR
 - Is planned to be used in the future
 - Implementation Consideration

It is important to clarify that a FAIR Supporting Resource might be of different types (e.g. EcoPortal is not only a registry for vocabularies but also an editor for metadata and a validation service).

The survey is accessible via the SIP Wizard (<https://sip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/>) and open for everybody who wants to contribute, as this is considered as an ongoing effort.

References

Magagna B, Schultes EA, Suchánek M, Kuhn T (2022) FIPs and Practice. *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 8: e94451. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e94451>